

The Fragile Foundations of the American Psychological Association's Position on Abortion and Mental Health, Which Rests on a Single Study: A Critical Examination of the Methodology, Selection Bias, and Interpretations of Gilchrist et al. (1995)

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Abstract

A 1995 study by Gilchrist *et al.* (hereinafter Gilchrist) has been highly influential in concluding that abortion does not increase psychiatric morbidity compared to carrying an unplanned pregnancy to term. This finding was adopted as the central basis for the American Psychological Association's (APA) official statements, adopted in 2008, regarding the safety of abortion from a mental health perspective. The APA has not revised that view or conducted a new literature review since 2008. Moreover, the APA has been clear that it has a political position on abortion as a basic civil right that is independent of any evidence regarding the risks or benefits of abortion to women's mental health. Still, this political view may influence the APA's willingness to recognize and acknowledge research demonstrating abortion's contribution to any significant negative mental health effects. Indeed, the APA's continued reliance on Gilchrist as evidence that abortion poses no significant risks to women is remarkable given (a) the large body of subsequent and better studies showing abortion is linked to higher rates of mental illnesses, and (b) the fact that Gilchrist was so fundamentally flawed in design and execution that it should never have been relied upon in the first place. This paper offers a complete examination of Gilchrist's limitations, spanning fundamental design flaws, problematic measurement of outcomes, inadequate control for confounding variables, issues with attrition and generalizability and selective reporting. In short, this paper demonstrates that the methodological constraints of Gilchrist render its findings insufficient as evidence justifying any broad clinical or policy conclusions. Therefore, the position statements of the

American Psychological Association, and other health organizations relying upon it, are not based on the best, or even reasonably good scientific evidence.

1. Introduction

Why does a 1995 study on abortion and mental health still matter today? Although many better studies have come out since, the conclusion of Gilchrist et al. (hereinafter Gilchrist)¹—that abortion does not increase the risk of mental health problems compared to giving birth to an unplanned child—still dominates public perceptions. This is because the American Psychological Association (APA) officially accepted these conclusions as central to their own 2008 Task Force on Mental Health and Abortion (TFMHA) conclusions.²

The history of the APA and TFMHA is important context. In 1968 the APA officially adopted a political position that abortion is a “civil right.”³ This was not based on evidence of psychological benefits to women, but purely as a civil rights position. Ever since then, the APA has been involved in pro-choice advocacy, including opposition to any regulation of abortion and advocacy for unrestricted access to abortion. According to Nancy Russo, an APA spokesperson on abortion issues, this political priority takes precedence, rendering any negative effects on women’s mental health “not relevant.”⁴ This advocacy on behalf of abortion, and similar politicized issues, has been criticized by APA insiders as resulting in a sacrifice of scientific rigor in favor of political advocacy.^{5,6}

This context explains the APA’s immediate opposition to Surgeon General Koop’s 1989 recommendation for a national prospective study to investigate the mental health risks of abortion. The APA argued that the safety and benefits of abortion were settled science and therefore, Koop’s recommendation for more research was unnecessary.⁷

But during the next two decades, a body of new studies began to accumulate that consistently revealed elevated levels of suicide,^{8,9} depression,^{10–12} substance misuse,^{13–16} and psychiatric treatment rates.^{12,17} Abortion advocates, both within and outside the APA, insisted these findings were identifying incidental associations, not anything that really matter to women or policy makers. To strengthen the credibility of this assertion, Division 35, Psychology of Women, decided to undertake a new systematic review of the literature on abortion and mental health in 2007. Contrary to normal APA practices, there was no call for nominations from members of the task force.¹⁸

Instead, the task force was selected entirely by Division 35 members. Most were publicly outspoken opponents of any government regulation of abortion, some had no publicly stated position on abortion, and a request for inclusion by an APA leader critical of abortion was rejected.¹⁸ The resulting TFMHA report, insisting there were no significant mental health risks associated with abortion, was adopted by the APA governing council in April of 2008, giving it the official stamp of the APA's approval.¹⁸

Notably, the TFMHA began with the presumption that abortion should be presumed generally safe and beneficial, absent definitive evidence that it was not. No evidence of any mental health benefits from abortion was offered. Instead, every study reporting higher rates of mental illness associated with abortion was dismissed as methodologically flawed. Therefore, TFMHA concluded that any findings of negative outcomes identified in any of the individual studies could be presumed to be indicative of the experiences of the general population. Upon review, they asserted that only a single study, Gilchrist, offered a sufficiently high-quality comparison of mental health treatment rates following abortion compared to other groups of women who also faced unplanned pregnancies.¹⁸

In brief, Gilchrist examined data provided by general practitioners (N=1,509) in England. These doctors recruited female volunteers (N=13,261) who authorized them to share information about their health with the study team. Gilchrist then compared new psychiatric diagnoses across four pregnancy groups: (a) induced abortion request granted and completed, (b) induced abortion request denied based on doctor's determination that the risks were greater than the benefits, (c) the woman requesting the abortion changed her mind, and (d) a group of women who faced an unplanned pregnancy but did not request an abortion. Based on their reported results, Gilchrist concluded there was "no overall increase in reported psychiatric morbidity" following abortion compared to childbirth.

Gilchrist became the cornerstone upon which TFMHA built its own conclusion that the rate of mental health problems is not affected by exposure to abortion. Specifically, TFMHA declared that "the relative risk of mental health problems among *adult* women who have a *single*, legal, *first-trimester* abortion of an *unwanted* pregnancy for nontherapeutic reasons is no greater than the risk among women who deliver an unwanted pregnancy" (italics added).

Notably, the qualifications embedded in this statement (italicized above) reflected admissions in the

body of the report that mental health may worsen for (a) minors, and (b) for women who have multiple abortions, and (c) those who have later term abortions, and (d) those who faced pressure to abort contrary to their own preferences. These and other risk factors were buried in only a few sentences in the body of the report but were not otherwise highlighted in any conclusions or summary statements. As a result, the nuances in the APA's summary statements were omitted in media reports stating that the APA review found that "abortion has no mental health risks," an oversimplification that APA officials never attempted to correct.¹⁹

Notably, the TFMHA's chair was abortion researcher Brenda Major, who both prior to and after the report refused to allow data from her own studies to be examined by others, a violation of the APA's own data-sharing ethics rules.²⁰ This withholding of data clearly suggests that Major's own studies involved selective reporting and an effort to prevent re-analyses of her data that might compromise her preferred narrative on abortion and mental health. This suggests that a similar bias was applied to the TFMHA report. Indeed, numerous literature reviews following the TFMHA report strongly criticized their methodology and conclusions.²¹⁻²³

Since 2008, a host of new studies have been published that have clearly demonstrated that abortion, in and of itself, is an independent risk factor for elevated rates of suicide,²²⁻²⁸ depression,^{23,29,30} substance misuse,^{22,25,26} bipolar disorder,^{23,25} postpartum psychiatric treatment rates,³¹ psychiatric hospitalization,^{25,32} demands on mental health services,^{33,34} and more.²³

But despite all this evidence, or perhaps because of it, the APA has not published any updated literature reviews. Nor has it changed its political position or advocacy for "abortion rights" in both legislatures and the courts. Moreover, in all of these advocacy efforts, APA lobbyists and lawyers continue to point to the 2008 TFMHA report, which in turn points to Gilchrist. In addition, other health care lobbying groups, like the American Medical Associations, also regularly point to the TFMHA report, and thereby, indirectly to Gilchrist.

Despite its enduring influence, Gilchrist's methodological limitations have received insufficient scholarly attention. A rigorous reappraisal reveals that the study's sampling methods, outcome measurements, and analytical choices preclude any broad generalization. The objective of this commentary is to synthesize these weaknesses to frame the study's findings within a more cautious and methodologically sound framework.

2. Fundamental Design & Selection Bias

2.1. Case Series Design (Non-Inception Cohort): Gilchrist et al. present their study as a prospective cohort, but it is more accurately classified as a case series. This is because women were identified and enrolled after their pregnancy outcome was determined (i.e., after deciding to seek or not seek an abortion), violating the temporal structure required for causal inference. A true prospective cohort study would follow a study group identified before they became pregnant, and certainly before any decisions about proceeding with the pregnancy had occurred.

In this study, recruitment happened only after women had already sought care and, in many cases, after they had decided on — or even completed — their pregnancy outcome. This means that enrollment was conditional on a factor that could be influenced by the exposure itself (or closely related to it), which can create what's known as collider stratification bias. This design also introduces post-treatment selection bias, as both prior psychiatric history and degrees of emotional stress at the time of recruitment could well influence who consented to participate and who did not.

The design is more accurately classified as a prospective case series.³⁵ This is an important distinction: the size of the population 'at risk' of the exposure (each pregnancy outcome) can not be accurately estimated in case series. Therefore, while rates within each group can be calculated, they cannot be fairly compared to estimate how they may differ in the general population. In short, case series are helpful for developing hypotheses but not for evidence that supports any generalizations.

2.2. Non-Representative and Biased Sampling (GP and Patient Level): This study relied on a non-random sample of 1,509 volunteer GPs, who then recruited a convenience sample of their own patients. This introduces a high risk of selection bias. GPs with strong views on abortion may have been more likely to participate, and their clinical judgments—including referrals for termination and subsequent psychiatric diagnoses—could be systematically biased. Their own ideological leanings may also have influenced which women they chose to invite into the study influenced which women they chose to invite.

The potential for ideological bias among GPs was further exacerbated by the possibility of both ideological and emotional self-selection and self-censure bias among the women themselves.

Women experiencing—or anticipating—negative psychological reactions may have been more likely to decline participation, either to avoid stigma or due to emotional distress. This introduces a skewed sample that likely underrepresents those most vulnerable to adverse outcomes.

An indication of the sample's non-representativeness is that 48.3% of participants had abortions, a rate far exceeding the contemporary UK population rate of ~22.8%. This suggests that the sample is not generalizable to all women with unplanned pregnancies.

2.3. Potential for Non-Response Bias at Patient Recruitment: Participation required women to “agree to their family doctor supplying anonymous data.” The authors note that in a pilot survey, nearly half of women who had a termination said they would refuse to participate if anonymity was not guaranteed. This indicates that a significant proportion of women, particularly those who may have experienced shame, regret, or trauma, likely declined to participate. This initial non-response bias systematically excludes the very subpopulation most likely to experience negative outcomes, leading to a probable underestimation of psychiatric morbidity in the abortion group.

3. Group Contamination & Disproportionate Attrition

3.1. Ambiguous Definition of "Unplanned Pregnancy": The cohort was defined by “unplanned pregnancy,” a construct with critical implications for comparing mental health outcomes. However, the definition—“unintended or one in which the woman could not state, to within 3 months, the duration of her attempts to conceive”—is clinically ambiguous. It conflates women with strongly unintended pregnancies with those who were merely ambivalent or not meticulously planning. The psychological stakes and baseline risk for these subgroups are likely vastly different, introducing noise and potential misclassification bias at the cohort's foundation.

In addition, the unplanned pregnancy group included (a) women who were surprised but happy to discover they were pregnant, (b) women who were ambivalent and may have considered abortion but not to the degree they sought one, (c) women who may have sought an abortion elsewhere and either changed their minds or were declined an abortion and subsequently saw a different GP for prenatal care, (d) women who had an unhappy prior abortion and were disinclined to have another, (e) women with a history of one or more prior miscarriages, and (f) women facing any other different circumstance. As a result, this general catch-all group includes very different psychological experiences into one group and does not provide a clear and reliable control group with which to contrast the potential mental health impact of abortion.

3.2. Inappropriate Comparison Group Construction: The comparison groups were not cleanly separated. Most problematically, Gilchrist allowed women with a history of abortions to be included in all four groups. A substantial portion of women who carried to term, for example, had a history of prior or subsequent abortions. Exposure to abortion, before or after the index pregnancy, contaminated the comparison groups and increased the likelihood of null findings since any mental health effects associated with abortion would appear in every group.

Similarly, miscarriage and natural losses are known to be associated with increased risk of mental health problems similar to those associated with induced abortions. But the primary comparison group (“did not request termination”) included women who had miscarriages, which is known to put women at elevated risk for psychological distress. Failing segregate and control differences associated with prior, current and subsequent miscarriages would again contaminate group comparisons and tend to obscure any mental health differences due to abortion and/or natural losses. It would have been better to report results for three groups: abortion, natural loss, and live birth.

3.3. High and Differential Attrition Rates: Follow-up was poor and uneven. By the study’s end, 65.6% of the abortion group and 57.6% of the non-abortion group were lost. Attrition was higher among younger, single, more educated women—a demographic more likely to seek abortion. Women experiencing negative psychological outcomes may have been more likely to drop out (e.g., by changing doctors), leading to a systematic underestimation of morbidity in the abortion group.

4. Imprecise and Limited Outcome Measures

4.1. Non-Standardized and Imprecise Outcome Measurement (GP Diagnosis): Psychiatric morbidity was assessed via GP reports using ICD-8 codes, without standardized diagnostic instruments or validation by mental health specialists. The authors themselves identified this as a “major disadvantage,” admitting to “under-recognition and an imprecise diagnosis of psychiatric disorder.”

This weakness is starkly illustrated by the GP’s reporting 225 cases of “puerperal psychosis,” a rate far higher than national rates. Almost all cases of puerperal psychosis normally result in hospitalization, but the participating GP’s reported that only 13 of the 225 cases they reported

resulted in hospitalization. This suggests that the GP's reported far more cases of "puerperal psychosis" than treating psychiatrists would have reported. This degree of diagnostic imprecision (a ~17-fold over-estimation of severe psychosis) suggests that more common disorders like depression and anxiety may also have been misclassified.

In addition, the study did not account for clustering by GP. Patients nested within the same practice may share contextual factors—such as GP attitudes, local resources, or referral patterns—that violate assumptions of independence. Ignoring this clustering can lead to underestimated standard errors and inflated confidence in null findings

4.2 Failure to Account for Timing, Severity, and Recurrence of Morbidity: The analysis only captured the first reported episode of illness in each diagnostic category. It provided no data on the duration, severity, number of recurrences, or precise timing of episodes relative to the pregnancy event. This approach dilutes the analysis, obscuring potential patterns—such as a clustering of illness proximate to the abortion—that could support a causal inference and fails to capture the full clinical burden of morbidity.

The failure to investigate how pre-existing mental health problems were affected by the pregnancy outcome is especially problematic. There is no reason to believe that prior mental health issues, such as depression or anxiety, are unaffected by either abortion or delivery of an unplanned pregnancy. Indeed, the question of how different pregnancy outcomes might worsen or lessen pre-existing mental health issues is central to any investigation on the effects of abortion on mental health. Gilchrist's conclusions regarding null findings relative to first diagnoses wrongly imply that there are unlikely to be differences in the course of preexisting conditions.

In addition, given this focus on first new diagnoses, the computation of risk ratios was not the most appropriate analytic strategy. From a technical standpoint, time-to-first-event analyses (survival analysis) are commonly preferred because they account for varying follow-up times and enable hazard ratio estimation. Recurrent-event models—such as Andersen-Gill or Prentice-Williams-Peterson—are better suited to capturing total morbidity burden when multiple episodes per subject occur. These approaches would allow for a more accurate and clinically meaningful assessment of psychiatric risk over time.

4.3. Narrow Focus on Severe Outcomes: The study focused primarily on severe outcomes

(psychosis, hospital admission) and deliberate self-harm (DSH). It did not systematically measure more common but less severe conditions such as sub-clinical depression, anxiety, adjustment disorders, or substance abuse. This narrow focus risks missing a significant portion of the psychological sequelae associated with pregnancy outcomes, creating a false narrative.

5. Inadequate Attention to Confounding Variables

5.1. Failure to Control for Common Confounding Variables: While the study adjusted for basic demographics, it lacked data on critical confounding variables strongly associated with both abortion and mental health outcomes, such as socioeconomic status, exposure to intimate partner violence, quality of social support, and childhood adversity. These factors are known to influence both the likelihood of abortion and mental health outcomes, and their omission severely limits the study's ability to adjust for confounding.

Moreover, the study did not account for time-varying confounders—variables that change over the course of the study and may be influenced by the exposure itself. For example, relationship status, financial stress, subsequent pregnancy outcomes or changes in social support may evolve after the pregnancy outcome and in turn affect psychiatric risk. Failure to model these dynamics can result in biased estimates and misleading conclusions.

5.2. Failure to Identify Key Risk Factors: The methodology could not account for well-documented risk factors for post-abortion distress, such as feeling pressured by others into the decision, experiencing moral or religious conflict, or having a strong maternal desire for the child. If women who were exposed to these risk factors were underrepresented in the sample, this would bias the findings toward null results.

6. Inappropriate Statistical Methods

6.1. Lack of Power for Key Comparisons: The authors acknowledged the study had “little power to detect important effects” in two of the four groups: women refused abortion and those who changed their minds. This precludes meaningful conclusions about the mental health outcomes of having a wanted abortion denied or choosing to continue a pregnancy after initially considering abortion.

6.2. Weak Statistical Methods: Gilchrist et al. employed statistical methods that are poorly suited to sparse data and rare outcomes. Their use of large-sample approximations and the “sum of reciprocals” method for confidence intervals which is problematic when event counts are low. These techniques can produce misleading estimates and overly narrow confidence intervals.³⁶ More reliable results should have been sought using Koopman’s Method, binomial (exact) methods, or maximum likelihood estimation (MLE) with profile-likelihood confidence intervals. The failure to use appropriate methods undermines the credibility of the reported null findings.

7. Selective Reporting & Non-generalizable findings

7.1. Omission of Critical Data: The study collected data on patient deaths but the authors chose not to report the causes or distribution across groups. This is a critical omission, as record-linkage studies from other countries (e.g., Finland) have found significantly higher mortality rates, including from suicide, following abortion compared to childbirth. The absence of this data obscures the full risk profile and undermines the study’s transparency.

Given the study’s focus on psychiatric outcomes, the suppression of mortality data—especially suicide—represents a serious lapse in reporting. It is unclear whether this omission was due to low event counts, lack of statistical power, or other reasons, but its exclusion prevents a complete assessment of harm.

7.2. Limited Generalizability to Other Countries: The study was conducted under the UK’s Abortion Act (1967), which requires two physicians to certify that continuation of the pregnancy poses a greater risk to mental/physical health of the woman than an abortion. This selection filter led to approximately 10% of women undergoing abortion decision review being denied abortions. This group likely included women who were most clearly at the greatest risk of increased psychiatric distress following an abortion, perhaps one that is coerced and contrary to their own values, may be helped to pursue a different option. This protective filter is absent in countries like the United States where there are no requirements for pre-abortion risk assessments, severely limiting the generalizability of the findings to those contexts.

8. Overstated and Selective Conclusions

8.1. Null Findings Were Stretched into Overstated Conclusions: The authors’ central conclusion was that there is “no overall increase in reported psychiatric morbidity after termination,” But this

is an overly broad assertion that is not supported by the study's design or data. The methodological flaws—non-random sampling, post-exposure enrollment, narrow outcome scope, and weak statistical methods—biased the study toward null results that undermine causal inference.

The framing of null findings as evidence of safety is especially misleading. Absence of evidence is not evidence of absence, particularly when the study is underpowered, poorly controlled, and structurally biased. The authors' interpretation fails to acknowledge the limitations inherent in their design and analysis.

8.2. Significant Findings Were Given Too Little Attention: Notably, the observed increase in deliberate self-harm among the subset of aborting women with no prior psychiatric history is downplayed in the paper as likely due to confounding. The authors' conclusion that increased deliberate self-harm was due to "adverse social factors" is speculative, as these specific psychological mediators were unmeasured. The observed effects could be directly related to the abortion experience itself in the context of internal conflict. While confounding is possible, the presence of a statistically significant increased risk of self-harm should have required the authors to recommend further investigation, not dismissal of these results.

8.3. No evidence of any benefit from abortion. The authors state that the most frequent reason for an abortion referral was "previous or anticipated psychiatric illness." Yet, their own results show that abortion did not reduce the risk of new psychiatric diagnosis relative to delivery of unplanned pregnancies. Women with a prior psychiatric history were at the highest risk of new psychiatric diagnoses *regardless of outcome*. Abortion failed to be a protective intervention.

This absence of any finding of benefit is especially striking given the selection bias issues in the sample which were disproportionately likely to exclude women who were most likely to be harmed and to include women most likely to be benefited.

This lack of benefit was not discussed by the authors. This underscores a clear case of circular logic in the study design and conclusions: psychiatric risk is used to justify abortion, and then the absence of observed harm is taken as proof of benefit.

9. Quality grading and study classification

9.1. Quality assessment when treated as a cohort study: Gilchrist et al. described their design as a prospective cohort study. The Newcastle-Ottawa Scale for cohort studies is a commonly used tool for grading the quality of such studies.³⁷ It grades studies based on three domains; 1) selection of study groups or how well sample represents the target population, (four points); 2) comparability of groups, and account for confounders (two points); and 3) ascertainment of exposure and outcomes, how measured (three points). At best, Gilchrist would receive 5 of the 9 possible points, indicating a low to middling level of study quality.

Table 1: NOS Scoring for Gilchrist

NOS Domain and Items	Response	Notes informing the Response
<u>Selection</u>		
1. Representativeness of the exposed cohort	No (0)	Recruited only from volunteer GPs and volunteer women; not population-based.
2. Selection of the non-exposed cohort	Yes (1)	Drawn from the same GP practices; same community.
3. Ascertainment of exposure	Yes (1)	A pregnancy outcome was confirmed by the reporting GP and medical records.
4. Demonstration that outcome not present at baseline	No (0)	Many women had prior psychiatric histories; no exclusion or full adjustment.
<u>Comparability</u>		
1. Comparability of cohorts on design/analysis	Partial (1 of 2)	Adjusted for some variables (age, marital status, smoking, education age, gravidity, prior abortion), but omitted key psychosocial confounders (miscarriages, subsequent

NOS Domain and Items	Response	Notes informing the Response
		abortions, partner coercion, trauma, support).
<u>Outcome</u>		
1. Assessment of outcome	Yes (1)	Psychiatric outcomes reported by GPs (ICD-8)
2. Follow-up long enough for outcomes	Yes (1)	Up to 8 years of follow-up; sufficient period for psychiatric morbidity to manifest.
3. Adequacy of follow-up	No (0)	High attrition (~66% abortion group, 58% non-abortion group) with inadequate description of non-responders.
<u>Total NOS Score</u>	5/9	Low methodological quality.

9.2. Quality assessment when treated as a case series: But Gilchrist classification of the study as a cohort study should not be accepted at face value. Indeed, it is common for case series studies to be misidentified as cohort study [cite]. When the sampling methodology is examined more closely, Gilchrist study is seen to be more properly classified as an outcome-ascertained case series. In a true prospective cohort study, participants are recruited before they are exposed to any variables predictive of the outcomes being tested. But in the Gilchrist study, women were recruited only after they had already made decisions about pregnancy resolution (termination, continuation, refusal, or change of mind). This post-exposure recruitment violates the inception principle of true cohorts, in which subjects are identified before exposure and followed forward. The absence of a defined sampling denominator further precludes valid estimation of incidence rates. By epidemiologic standards (Dekkers et al., 2012), Gilchrist should therefore be classified as a case series with comparison groups rather than a cohort study.

Based on this conclusion, the Joanna Briggs Institute (JBI) Critical Appraisal Checklist for Case Series is a more appropriate study quality assessment tool.³⁸ When this checklist is applied to Gilchrist et al (Table 2), it is revealed to perform poorly across most domains. The checklist highlights the study's lack of representativeness, incomplete reporting, and methodological weaknesses.

Table 2: JBI Case Series Rating

JBI Critical Appraisal Item	Response (Yes/No/Unclear)	Notes informing the Response
1. Were there clear criteria for inclusion in the case series?	No	Participants recruited only after exposure decision via non-random GP sample; inclusion criteria not systematically applied.
2. Was the condition measured in a standard, reliable way for all participants?	Yes	Psychiatric morbidity coded using ICD-8 categories, applied consistently across groups.
3. Were valid methods used for identification of the condition for all participants?	Unclear	ICD-8 is a valid classification system, but assessments were made by GPs, not psychiatrists; risk of diagnostic misclassification acknowledged by authors.
4. Did the case series have consecutive inclusion of participants?	No	Recruitment depended on voluntary GP reporting; consecutive inclusion cannot be established.
5. Did the case series have complete inclusion of participants?	No	Limited to patients of participating GPs; no attempt to capture all eligible women nationally.
6. Was there clear reporting of the demographics of the participants in	Unclear	Basic demographics (age, parity, smoking) were used for adjustment but not fully reported

JBI Critical Appraisal Item	Response (Yes/No/Unclear)	Notes informing the Response
the study?		in detail.
7. Was there clear reporting of clinical information of the participants?	No	Prior abortion history within comparison groups incompletely reported, leading to contamination of reference groups.
8. Were the outcomes or follow-up results of cases clearly reported?	Unclear	Some outcomes (psychiatric morbidity) reported, but critical endpoints (timing of events, mortality) omitted.
9. Was there clear reporting of the presenting site(s)/clinic(s) demographic information?	No	GP practice demographics, geographic distribution, and catchment characteristics not described.
10. Was statistical analysis appropriate?	Unclear	Statistical approach adequate for crude comparisons, but variance estimation, handling of clustering, and small subgroup analyses were methodologically weak.

Overall JBI appraisal: Low methodological quality.

This appraisal reinforces the conclusion that Gilchrist et al. is not a high-quality cohort but a low-grade case series with significant risk of bias and incomplete reporting. Its findings should be weighted accordingly in evidence syntheses and not treated as decisive evidence for clinical or policy recommendations.

Both study quality assessments converge on the same conclusion: Gilchrist et al. (1995) does not provide high-quality evidence, whether interpreted as a flawed cohort or as a case series. The evidentiary weight of its findings should therefore be downgraded in systematic reviews, meta-

analyses, and policy deliberations.

9.3. Implications of grading. This grading reinforces the conclusion that Gilchrist et al. does not meet the standards required for population-based causal inference. While large in sample size, the structural flaws in design, execution, and reporting place it at the lower tier of observational evidence. By contrast, later registry-linkage studies in Finland, Denmark, and the U.S., which employ inception cohorts, complete follow-up, and validated psychiatric endpoints, achieve substantially higher methodological grades.

Thus, Gilchrist's findings should not be weighted as decisive evidence in meta-analyses or policy statements. At best, the study provides a historical data point illustrating the limitations of volunteer-based GP reporting systems, not a reliable estimate of the psychiatric consequences of abortion.

Conclusion

The Gilchrist et al. (1995) study is characterized by a cascade of methodological limitations that span its design, measurement, analysis, and interpretation. Its non-representative sampling, imprecise outcome measurement, inadequate control for confounding, and high attrition collectively render its findings highly susceptible to bias and severely limit their generalizability.

Gilchrist does not provide a reliable basis for the definitive conclusion that abortion does not elevate risk for psychiatric morbidity compared to childbirth. Most importantly, the conclusions of Gilchrist conflict with the findings of better designed studies, including large-scale, record-linkage studies in Canada,²⁵ Finland,⁸ Denmark,³² and the United States,^{26,30,31,33,34} which have consistently found significantly higher rates of mental health care utilization, psychiatric hospitalization, and suicide associated with abortion compared to childbirth.

Gilchrist's continued, though often indirect, citation through the APA's TFMHA report, without adequate acknowledgment of these flaws is a disservice to the scientific and clinical community.

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